

LOGISTICS-BASED MANAGEMENT OF ENTERPRISE PRODUCT ASSORTMENT THROUGH VALUE CHAIN BUSINESS PROCESS ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Theoretical approaches to defining the content of product assortment management processes at the enterprise level have been generalized based on the analysis of the business process chain involved in new value creation. Recommendations are provided for assessing the feasibility of modifying the company's product assortment by identifying changes within the logistics chain of value-creating business processes.

Keywords: logistics, logistics management, product assortment, business process, value creation.

Introduction. The product assortment policy includes specific actions company management takes to meet the actual demand of target customer groups (market segments). These actions help form a product range that is both commercially effective and aligned with planned sales goals. Creating an optimal assortment of goods and services means organizing related business processes in the proper order and location. This is made possible by the stable work of the company's logistics system. The logistics system, in turn, covers the full cycle of creating new value – from finding ways to finance the business, buying necessary materials, transporting and storing them, processing them, storing and distributing the final products, selling them, receiving income, and paying back loans.

Literature Review. The theoretical and methodological foundations of logistics-based product assortment management have been explored by well-known economists such as Andrade R. [3], Camp R. [4], Guban A. [5], Hryhorak M. [1], Kasa R. [5], Khalifakh A. [2], Kotler P. [7], Lane K. [7], Lenskold J. [6], Lucato W. [3], Pylipenko A. [2], Sadler I. [8], Vanalle R. [3], Vieira-Jr. M. [3], Warren K. [9], and others. However, some specific aspects of assessing competitiveness – especially those related to how the value creation chain is formed – are still not well studied and require further research.

This study aims to provide a theoretical foundation and develop recommendations for logistics-based management of a company's product assortment based on analyzing the business process chain involved in creating new value.

Research Findings. The product assortment policy, implemented at different levels of enterprise management, involves strategic decisions regarding the product mix selection and tactical decisions for its ongoing optimization. It is important to note that while assortment policy goals may vary by enterprise, the most common ones include meeting customer needs – one of the key marketing principles that support deep market segmentation and differentiation and ensure close customer relationships; making optimal use of the company's technological expertise and experience; improving financial performance – where the assortment is formed based on expected profitability and profit volume; attracting new customers by expanding the use of the existing production program. This approach is

somewhat conservative, as it focuses on short-term results and aims to extend the lifecycle of outdated products by entering new markets. Another important goal is maintaining flexibility, based on a conglomerate structure of strategic business units and product ranges that depend on different technologies and require diverse economic, cultural, and political conditions. Also important is the principle of synergy, which involves expanding the company's production and services linked through common technologies, shared employee expertise, or other logical connections.

An enterprise needs to pursue a product assortment policy that regularly updates its product range to better meet the potential needs of consumers, while doing so within the framework of its existing assortment in order to minimize the costs of such updates. In this sense, product assortment policy is a dynamic system that is constantly evolving and must be managed with consideration for changing market demands.

Traditional approaches to managing a company's product assortment are based on analyzing the external environment and matching emerging opportunities with the company's available resources to identify new product types and define assortment rules. However, companies that follow this approach often face significant challenges: first, they must evaluate a large number of options; and second, developing new products and promoting them to the market requires substantial financial resources – resources these companies may lack.

Another limitation of this approach is that it mainly focuses on consumer markets, while other players in the same industry are not considered as potential customers. These players may include those who form the so-called "five forces" of competition in the enterprise's market environment.

The greatest potential for expanding a company's product assortment often lies among its competitors. This is due to several factors. Competitors typically use similar technologies in production, sales, and customer service, which opens up significant opportunities for collaboration. The more complex and diversified a company's value chain is (such as in mechanical engineering, instrumentation, software development, etc.), the greater the potential for product line expansion. A

highly competitive market also creates more opportunities for assortment growth and for strengthening the company's market position. Establishing business relationships with competitors can also provide valuable insights into their operations – often at low cost or even to the company's advantage.

Let us now take a closer look at how this proposed approach to identifying new product opportunities can be applied. First, it is important to recall that, according to the resource-based view of the production system, each enterprise has several key types of resources: technical, technological, human, spatial, informational, and financial.

The interaction and transformation of these resources into products and services occur through the company's value chain or chain of business processes. Historically, these tools were applied to large enterprises, where the value chain was built for individual functional departments or product lines. However, for small and medium-sized enterprises, it is reasonable to construct a value chain for the enterprise as a whole. If the company has a highly diversified product assortment, it may be appropriate to develop several separate value chains for different product groups serving different markets.

In this approach, each intermediate product generated at any stage of the value chain (or a set of stages) can potentially be treated as an independent product or service – something that directly interacts with the customer.

Subsequent stages involve assessing the potential demand for such products or services within the company's existing target market segments. It is also necessary to examine the feasibility of promoting these offerings to new segments of the target market. In some cases, such a strategic pivot may align more effectively with the enterprise's resource base – for example, the company may shift toward serving those who were formerly considered competitors. This repositioning would enable the enterprise to preserve its competitive advantages while entering (or even shaping) a market segment characterized by less intense competitive pressure. Such a transition, however, would require a significant revision of the company's overall strategy.

Value chain analysis further supports strategic decision-making related to the classic “make-or-buy” dilemma. Within this context, the value chain is examined through the lens of identifying the key elements that drive product (or firm-level) competitiveness. The aim is to determine which types of activities (i.e., business processes) produce intermediate outputs that can feasibly be sourced from the external market. Frequently, such suppliers are also competitors. Outsourcing specific intermediate products may be justified by two strategic considerations: on the one hand, it enables the firm to concentrate its resources on operations that

most directly contribute to sustaining and enhancing the competitiveness of both individual products and the enterprise as a whole; on the other hand, outsourcing reduces exposure to market risks – for instance, when fulfilling a large-scale order, the firm may avoid the need for capital investments, the cost of those investments, and the potential risk of order cancellation by the client.

When deciding to source intermediate products from the market, the firm must also determine the optimal number of suppliers in order to minimize the risk of non-fulfillment. This issue must be addressed in parallel with the objective of maximizing volume-based discounts. Since optimal outcomes for these two tasks often diverge, a compromise solution must be sought. Such a solution depends on two main groups of factors: the degree to which delivery lead time is a critical parameter for the firm's customers, and the price elasticity of the supplier's unit cost with respect to order volume.

The potential benefits of the proposed approach are most clearly realized when the enterprise possesses a complex and well-developed value chain. Based on the outlined approach, decisions concerning the modification of the product assortment should be preceded by a comprehensive analysis across the following evaluation dimensions.

First, the likelihood and consequences of replacing in-house production of a specific intermediate product with external procurement must be assessed in terms of its impact on the enterprise's competitiveness. This involves identifying the factors that distinguish the enterprise in customers' eyes – such as product quality, order fulfillment speed, or customization capabilities.

Second, it is essential to evaluate the expected changes in cost structure resulting from such a replacement. This assessment determines whether the decision is economically beneficial on a direct (transactional) level – i.e., whether outsourcing is more profitable than internal production.

Third, the broader implications of the replacement must be projected – particularly, whether the change, while potentially unprofitable at the transaction level, contributes to increased sales volumes of final products and, consequently, to higher overall profits.

Fourth, the enterprise must identify the market risks associated with the proposed logistics transformation, including supplier dependency, potential disruptions, and volatility in procurement conditions.

The approach described herein is applicable in the practical analysis and modification of product assortments in small and medium-sized enterprises, particularly within the context of the Ukrainian economy. A visualization of the key components of the proposed approach is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Logistic management of product assortment framework based on business process value chain analysis (author's proposal)

Fig. 1 illustrates the integrated framework for logistic management of product assortment through value chain analysis. The diagram depicts the systematic approach to assortment modification decisions based on business process evaluation. The upper section displays the value creation business process chain, consisting of six interconnected core processes: procurement, production, logistics, distribution, service, and finance. This continuous chain represents the foundation upon which value is created throughout the enterprise.

The central portion of the diagram represents the analytical phase where the value chain is examined to identify opportunities for product assortment modification. This analysis flows downward to the evaluation criteria section, where four key assessment dimensions are highlighted: (1) impact assessment on company competitiveness, (2) determination of changes in cost structure, (3) forecasting the impact on overall profitability, and (4) assessment of company's market risks.

The lower section illustrates three strategic decisions that emerge from this evaluation: the "make or buy" decision concerning intermediate products, the potential to convert intermediate products into independent goods, and opportunities for entry into new market segments. External influences from both the market environment and competitors (indicated by dashed arrows) affect the entire decision-making process. The framework culminates in product assortment optimization, representing the ultimate goal of the logistic management approach.

Conclusions. Product assortment policy is a dynamic system continuously evolving and must be reviewed in light of changing market demands. Decisions regarding the modification of a company's product assortment require a comprehensive evaluation of changes within the business process chain across several key dimensions: analysis of product-related competitive advantages, structural transformations in cost and expenditure composition, assessment of changes in

marginal profitability, and identification of market risks associated with logistical adjustments.

Future research will focus on developing methodological tools for analyzing the logistics chain of value-creating business processes.

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